

DEFORMATIONS DUE TO EXPLOSIVE AND IMPLOSIVE LOADS OF SANDWICH CYLINDERS USING THIRD ORDER SHEAR AND NORMAL DEFORMABLE THEORY (TSNDT)

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ABSTRACT

We use an equivalent single layer third order shear and normal deformable shell theory (TSNDT) to study deformations of a linear elastic sandwich cylinder under implosive and explosive loads applied on a part of the cylinder mantle. In the TSNDT the three displacement components at a point are expressed as complete polynomials of degree three in the thickness coordinate. We find in-plane stresses from the constitutive relations and the TSNDT displacement field, and compute transverse stresses by using a stress recovery scheme in which the 3-dimensional (3-D) equations for the balance of linear momentum are integrated over the thickness of the cylinder. No shear correction factor is used. We first compare results predicted by the TSNDT with those obtained by analyzing 3-D deformations with the finite element commercial software, ABAQUS, and establish that the TSNDT gives accurate results by using considerably fewer degrees of freedom than those needed for solving the problem by the finite element method and the 3-D linear elasticity theory. It is found that bending deformations are dominant in the face sheets but transverse shear deformations in the core for both explosive and implosive loads.

1 INTRODUCTION

An explosion in air or water induces an instantaneous rise in the pressure and the temperature of the medium surrounding the explosion resulting in a compressive shock wave that applies an impulsive load of high intensity but short duration on a structure in the proximity of the explosion. A submerged vessel containing air or gas at low pressure may implode due to the compressive load acting on its wall by the depth pressure of the surrounding water. Thus the pressure in the water surrounding the imploding body suddenly drops which exerts an explosive shock load on a marine structure near the implosion. The shock waves generated by either an explosion or an implosion in water can catastrophically damage a nearby marine structure. For more details of underwater explosion and its possible damage to ships, readers are directed to the article by Keil [1]. LeBlanc et al. have reviewed the mechanics of underwater implosion [2].

Sandwich structures have emerged as promising light weight structures to withstand blast loads. A sandwich structure typically consists of a thick flexible honeycomb or metallic foam core backed by relatively thin fiber-reinforced face sheets on its top and bottom. When a sandwich structure is subjected to either an implosive or an explosive shock load, the core undergoes large deformations and absorbs a significant amount of energy which imparts the structure a high blast resistance. Xue and Hutchinson [3] have studied 3-dimensional (3-D) deformations of clamped monolithic and sandwich beams subjected to blast loads using the finite element method (FEM). For the sandwich beam the momentum impulse was applied to the outer surface facing the blast whereas for the monolithic beam it was distributed uniformly through the thickness of the beam. The results of their study demonstrated

that the sandwich beam has superior blast resistance than the monolithic beam of the same mass when subjected to a water blast load. Fleck and Deshpande [4] have developed an approximate analytical methodology to analyze dynamic response of a metallic sandwich beam subjected to air and water blast loads considering fluid-structure interaction. They achieved an order of magnitude improvement in the blast resistance of the beam by employing the sandwich construction for the case of water blast but only a moderate improvement for the case of air blast. Qui et al. [5] studied the same problem as that analyzed by Fleck and Deshpande [4] but used the FEM. However, they ignored the fluid-structure interaction and applied pressure-time histories representative of blast loads uniformly to the outer surface of the beam. The results of their study were found to agree well with the analytical predictions of Fleck and Deshpande [4]. Karagiozova et al. [6] analyzed the behavior of clamped metallic sandwich panels with aluminium honeycomb core subjected to blast loads using the FEM and by simulating the blast load as a time-dependent pressure.

Zhu et al. [7] studied dynamic response of sandwich panels with aluminium foam core under a blast load by conducting air-blast experiments and by employing the FEM. They also performed a parametric study to delineate effects of various geometric, material and loading parameters on the energy absorbed by the structure. Shen et al. [8] performed air-blast experiments on curved clamped aluminium sandwich panels with aluminium foam core and demonstrated a superior performance of the curved sandwich shell to that of a monolithic panel and of a flat sandwich plate. Radford et al. [9] experimentally demonstrated higher shock resistance to blast loads of aluminium foam cored clamped sandwich plates than that of their monolithic counterparts of equal mass. Liu et al. [10] studied deformations of sandwich cylinders with metallic face sheets and graded aluminium core under an air blast load.

A significant portion of the work related to sandwich structures under blast loads has focused on either flat or open curved geometries such as beams, plates and panels and a very few investigators have considered a complete cylindrical geometry. Sandwich cylinders are commonly used in aircraft and marine constructions and may be subjected to either implosive or explosive shock loads. Here, we study transient linear elastic deformations of sandwich cylinders subjected to such loads on a part of their mantle using a third order shear and normal deformable shell theory (TSNDT) and by considering the sandwich structure as an equivalent single layer of a homogeneous material. We use the FEM in the space domain and the finite difference method (FDM) in the time domain to solve the equations governing the transient deformations of the cylinder. The TSNDT represents the three displacement components at a point in the cylinder as complete polynomials of degree three in the thickness coordinate and is a special case of a K^{th} order plate theory (when $K = 3$) derived by Batra and Vidoli [11] using the Hellinger-Prange-Reissner principle [12]. The TSNDT considers transverse normal strain, cubic distribution of shear strains through the cylinder thickness, and does not require a shear correction factor. For monolithic structures, one can compute stresses directly from the constitutive relations. However, for laminated structures, transverse stresses found using the stress recovery scheme are more accurate than those found using the constitutive relations. In problems involving normal and tangential tractions on the cylinder mantle the traction boundary conditions can be well satisfied.

2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a sandwich cylinder, shown in Fig. 1, composed of two face sheets and a core, not necessarily of equal thickness, perfectly bonded to each other, and made, respectively, of orthotropic and isotropic homogeneous and linear elastic materials. The material of the core is usually softer than that of the face sheets. Let the length, the total thickness and the mean radius of the cylinder be a , h and R , respectively. Let x_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) denote the cylindrical curvilinear coordinates such that $x_3 = 0$ and a represents two ends, and $x_1 = 0$ represents the mid-surface of the cylinder as depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Geometry and coordinate system of a sandwich cylinder

Let u_i be the component of displacement at a point $p(\mathbf{x})$ in the cylinder along the x_i -direction. The physical components of the infinitesimal strain tensor at point p in the cylindrical curvilinear coordinate system are given by [13]

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{11} &= \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_1}, \quad \epsilon_{22} = \frac{1}{(1+x_1/R)} \left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{u_1}{R} \right), \quad \epsilon_{33} = \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x_3} + \frac{u_1}{R}, \\ 2\epsilon_{12} &= \frac{1}{(1+x_1/R)} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_2} - \frac{u_2}{R} \right) + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_1}, \quad 2\epsilon_{13} = \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_3} - \frac{u_3}{R} + \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x_1}, \quad 2\epsilon_{23} = \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_3} + \frac{1}{(1+x_1/R)} \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x_2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{ii} ($i = 1, 2, 3$) is the normal strain along the x_i -direction, ϵ_{12} and ϵ_{13} are the transverse shear strains, and ϵ_{23} is the in-plane shear strain.

In the TSNDDT the displacement, u_i , at a point is expressed as a complete polynomial of degree 3 in x_1 that can be obtained by Taylor series expansion of u_i in the thickness coordinate, x_1 , up to order 3, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{d} = x_1^i \mathbf{d}_i \quad (i = 0, 1, 2, 3) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{d} = [u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3]^T$ and vectors of the displacement, the slope, the curvature, and the curvature gradient at a point on the mid-surface of the cylinder appearing in Eq. (2) are given, respectively, by

$$\mathbf{d}_0 = [u_{10} \ u_{20} \ u_{30}]^T, \quad \mathbf{d}_1 = [u_{11} \ u_{21} \ u_{31}]^T, \quad \mathbf{d}_2 = [u_{12} \ u_{22} \ u_{32}]^T \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{d}_3 = [u_{13} \ u_{23} \ u_{33}]^T. \quad (2.1)$$

Unless stated otherwise, a repeated index implies summation over the range of the index. The equation resulting from the substitution of Eq. (2.1) into Eq. (2) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u_i(x_1, x_2, x_3, t) &= u_{ij}(x_2, x_3, t) A_j(x_1) \quad (i = 1, 2, 3; j = 0, 1, 2, 3), \\ A_j &= x_1^j, \quad u_{i0} = u_i(0, x_2, x_3, t), \quad u_{i1} = \left. \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} \right|_{x_1=0}, \quad 2u_{i2} = \left. \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_1^2} \right|_{x_1=0}, \quad 6u_{i3} = \left. \frac{\partial^3 u_i}{\partial x_1^3} \right|_{x_1=0} \end{aligned}$$

where t denotes time.

We use Hamilton's principle, given by Eq. (3), to derive equations governing transient deformations of the cylinder.

$$\delta S = \delta \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (T_k - T_p) dt = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here t_0 and t_1 represent two arbitrary instances of time, δ is the variational operator, T_k is the kinetic energy of the cylinder, and T_p is the total potential energy comprising of the strain energy of the cylinder and the work done by the external load. The expressions for T_p (neglecting body forces) and T_k for the three layered sandwich cylinder are given by Eqs. (4) and (5), respectively.

$$T_p = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{\Omega^k} (\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^k)^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}^k d\Omega^k \right] - \int_{\bar{A}} \mathbf{d}^T \bar{\mathbf{f}} dA \quad (4)$$

$$T_k = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{\Omega^k} \rho^k (\dot{\mathbf{d}}^T \dot{\mathbf{d}}) d\Omega^k \right] \quad (5)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = [\epsilon_{11} \ \epsilon_{22} \ \epsilon_{33} \ 2\epsilon_{23} \ 2\epsilon_{13} \ 2\epsilon_{12}]^T \text{ and } \boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{33} \ \sigma_{23} \ \sigma_{13} \ \sigma_{12}]^T \quad (6)$$

are, respectively, 6-D vectors containing components of the infinitesimal strain tensor and the Cauchy stress tensor, the dot over a variable represents its derivative with respect to time, Ω^k and ρ^k represent the volume and the mass density of the k^{th} layer, and A is the part of the bounding surface of the cylinder on which surface traction, $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$, is specified. Points on the remainder of the boundary of the domain, Ω , occupied by the cylinder have either null tractions (i.e., are on a free surface) or have displacements prescribed on them. The work done by reaction forces at points of the boundary where displacements are prescribed is not included in Eq. (4) because there variations in the prescribed displacements are null.

The constitutive relation (Hooke's law) for a linear elastic material of layer k is given by

$$\sigma_{ij}^k = C_{ijmn}^k \epsilon_{mn}^k, \quad C_{ijmn}^k = C_{mnij}^k = C_{jimn}^k \quad (i, j, m, n = 1, 2, 3) \quad (7)$$

Here \mathbf{C}^k is the fourth-order elasticity tensor having 21 independent components for a general anisotropic material. For an orthotropic, a transversely isotropic and an isotropic material, the independent components of \mathbf{C}^k reduce to 9, 5 and 2, respectively. In the global coordinate axes (x_1, x_2, x_3) C_{ijmn}^k are computed by using the tensor transformation rules for the stress and the strain tensors.

We substitute in Eq. (4) for $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^k$ in terms of $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^k$ from Eq. (7), and write $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^k$ in terms of the generalized displacements, \mathbf{d}_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3$) defined on the mid-surface using Eqs. (1) and (2). Also in Eqs. (4) and (5) we substitute for \mathbf{d} in terms of \mathbf{d}_i from Eq. (2). We use expressions for T_p and T_k thus obtained in Eq. (3) and in the resulting expression we integrate with respect to x_1 over the thickness of the cylinder to obtain an integral equation for δS with the integrand defined on the mid-surface. The mid-surface of the cylinder is discretized into a finite element (FE) mesh of disjoint 8-node iso-parametric quadrilateral elements. Thus δS equals the sum of integrals over each element. Following the standard procedure we obtain equations governing the transient deformations of the cylinder as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{X}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{F} \quad \text{on } \Omega \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8) \mathbf{M} is the global consistent mass matrix, \mathbf{K} is the global stiffness matrix, \mathbf{X} is the global nodal degrees of freedom, and \mathbf{F} is the global load vector representing generalized forces at nodes that are work equivalent to the surface tractions applied on the outer, the inner, and the edge surfaces of the cylinder. We note that in computation of these matrices the integration with respect to x_1 over the

thickness of the cylinder is performed exactly using the standard functions available in the software, MATLAB. For a FE mesh of N nodes, before applying essential boundary conditions, the length of vector \mathbf{X} equals $12N$ since a node has 12 degrees of freedom. Equation (8) is solved with pertinent initial and boundary conditions. Initial displacement and velocity are given by

$$u_i(x_1, x_2, x_3, 0) = u_i^0(x_1, x_2, x_3) \text{ and } \dot{u}_i(x_1, x_2, x_3, 0) = \dot{u}_i^0(x_1, x_2, x_3) \quad (i = 1, 2, 3) \quad (9)$$

where u_i^0 and \dot{u}_i^0 are known functions of x_1, x_2 and x_3 .

We consider two types of boundary conditions (BCs), namely, clamped and traction free, specified on edges $x_3 = 0$ and a of the cylinder whose definitions in the 3-D LET are given by Eqs. (10.1) and (10.2), respectively, and their implementation in the TSNDT are given by Eqs. (11.1) and (11.2), respectively.

$$u_1 = 0, u_2 = 0, u_3 = 0 \quad (10.1)$$

$$\sigma_{13} = 0, \sigma_{23} = 0, \sigma_{33} = 0 \quad (10.2)$$

$$u_{ii} = 0, u_{2i} = 0, u_{3i} = 0 \quad (i = 0, 1, 2, 3) \quad (11.1)$$

$$M_{13}^i = 0, M_{23}^i = 0, M_{33}^i = 0 \text{ where } M_{n3}^i = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} x_1^i \sigma_{n3} dx_1, \quad (i = 0, 1, 2, 3, n = 1, 2, 3) \quad (11.2)$$

Displacement (or essential) boundary conditions applied at points on a cylinder edge are satisfied during the time-integration of the coupled 2nd order linear ordinary differential equations included in Eq. (8). For discussing numerical results, we use the more common notation and replace x_1, x_2 and x_3 by r, θ and z , respectively, and u_1, u_2 and u_3 by u, v and w , respectively. We note that according to the coordinate system defined in Fig. 1, the range of r is $[-0.5h, 0.5h]$ and θ is the curvilinear distance along the mean circumference of the cylinder.

3 VERIFICATION OF SOFTWARE/CODE

We consider a monolithic isotropic clamped cylinder with $h = 20$ mm, $R/h = 10$, $a/R = 3$, having values of material parameters given by Young's modulus $E = 210$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ and mass density $\rho = 7800$ kg/m³, and only the inner surface subjected to a uniform pressure exponentially decaying in time given by Eq. (12) below which is similar to a shock load caused by an underwater explosion as suggested by Cole [15].

$$P(t) = \begin{cases} P_0 t / 60, & t \leq 60 \\ P_0 e^{-\frac{(t-60)}{100}}, & t > 60 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Here t is time in μ s, and we set $P_0 = 1$ MPa. The cylinder is assumed to be initially at rest; thus initial displacements and velocities of all nodes equal zero. We use the conditionally stable central-difference method to integrate the coupled ordinary differential equations (ODEs) (8) governing the transient response of the cylinder. The stability of the computed solution depends on the time step size, Δt , used in the integration scheme. We ascertain the critical time step, Δt_{crit} , to achieve a stable solution from the value of the maximum angular natural frequency, ω_{max} , as $\Delta t_{crit} = 2 / \omega_{max}$ and take $\Delta t \leq 0.5 \Delta t_{crit}$. We verify results for transient deformations of the cylinder predicted by the TSNDT by comparing them with those obtained by analyzing the 3-D deformations with the commercial FE software, ABAQUS. The following average error norm is used for the comparison:

$$\|e\|_0 = \left[\int_{t_0}^{t_1} [\alpha_{3-D}(t) - \alpha_{\text{TSNDT}}(t)]^2 dt / \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \alpha_{3-D}^2(t) dt \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

where α_{3-D} and α_{TSNDT} are the solution parameters obtained from the 3-D LET and the TSNDT, respectively. The TSNDT and the 3-D LET solutions are obtained with 377 8-node 2-D quadrilateral and 360,000 8-node 3-D brick elements which correspond to 18,444 and 1,223,100 nodal degrees of freedom (DoFs), respectively. The value of ω_{\max} for the cylinder is found to be 4 rad/ μs , hence we take $\Delta t = 0.01 \mu\text{s}$ which is much smaller than $\Delta t_{\text{crit}} = 0.5 \mu\text{s}$. In Fig. 2(a),(b) we have displayed time histories of the radial displacement, u , the hoop stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, and the axial stress, σ_{zz} , at a point $(0, 0, 0.5a)$ on the mid-surface of the cylinder obtained by using the TSNDT and the corresponding 3-D LET FE solutions. Results from the two theories agree well with each other having the difference, $\|e\|_0$, between them of 8.66%, 9.25% and 7.45% for the displacement, the hoop stress and the axial stress, respectively, up to 800 μs . In Fig. 2(c) we have depicted time history of the radial stress, σ_{rr} , at the point L $(-0.5h, 0, 0.5a)$ on the inner surface of the cylinder and the corresponding applied traction. The traction boundary condition is well satisfied at L on the inner surface of the cylinder with $\|e\|_0 = 0.08$. In Fig. 2(d) we have plotted time histories of the strain energy of deformation and of the kinetic energy and compared their sum, i.e., the total energy with the work done by the external force; both should be equal for a transient elastic problem. The results show an excellent agreement between them with $\|e\|_0 = 0.005$ which provides another check on the accuracy of computed results. Furthermore, the strain energy of deformation and the kinetic energy computed from the TSNDT are found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained from the 3-D LET as evident from the plots of Fig. 2(d).

Figure 2: For a monolithic isotropic cylinder subjected to pressure on its inner surface as given by Eq. (12), time histories of (a) displacement, $u(0, 0, 0.5a)$, (b) hoop stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, and axial stress, σ_{zz} at $(0, 0, 0.5a)$, (c) radial stress, $\sigma_{rr}(-0.5h, 0, 0.5a)$, and (d) the strain energy of deformation, the kinetic energy, the total energy and the work done by the external force.

4 DEFORMATIONS DUE TO EXPLOSIVE AND IMPLOSIVE LOADS

We now analyze the transient response of a clamped sandwich cylinder with $h = 30$ mm, $R = 70$ mm and $a = 300$ mm, made of two 5 mm thick orthotropic face sheets with fibers oriented at 45° with respect to the z -axis and a 20 mm thick isotropic core, and subjected to explosive and implosive shock loads on a part of the cylindrical surface. The initial displacements and velocity of all points of the cylinder are assumed to be zero. We find the in-plane stresses ($\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, σ_{zz} , $\sigma_{\theta z}$) from the constitutive relations and compute the transverse shear ($\sigma_{r\theta}$, σ_{rz}) and the transverse normal (σ_{rr}) stresses by using a stress recovery scheme (SRS). In the SRS, the three equations for the balance of linear momentum are integrated with respect to r starting from the inner face with surface tractions prescribed there as “initial conditions”. At interfaces between two adjoining layers, the traction and the displacement continuity conditions are satisfied; the former because we have used the single layer theory and the latter during integration of equations for the linear momentum balance with respect to r . The difference between surface tractions thus computed and the applied surface tractions on the top surface is an indicator of the error in the numerical solution of the problem. Values of material parameters for the orthotropic face sheets with material principal axes coincident with the (r, θ, z) coordinate axes and the isotropic core are given by Eqs. (14) and (15), respectively.

$$E_1 = 251 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = 48 \text{ GPa}, E_3 = 7.5 \text{ GPa}, G_{12} = 13.6 \text{ GPa}, G_{13} = 12 \text{ GPa}, G_{23} = 4.7 \text{ GPa}, \quad (14)$$

$$v_{12} = 0.036, v_{13} = 0.25, v_{23} = 0.171, \rho = 1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$E = E_1 / 100, \nu = 0.2, \rho = 320 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad (15)$$

The explosive load acting only on the inner surface of the cylinder is simulated by applying a time-dependent and non-uniformly distributed pressure profile over a circular area, \bar{A} , of radius 10.6 cm in the θz -plane centered at the point $Q(-0.5h, 0.5b, 0.5a)$ on the inner surface of the cylinder. The pressure given by Eq. (16) is assumed to point radially outwards.

$$P(c, t) = \begin{cases} (-0.0005c^4 + 0.01c^3 - 0.0586c^2 - 0.001c + 1)P(t), & c < 10.6 \text{ cm} \\ 0, & c \geq 10.6 \text{ cm} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Here c is the curvilinear distance in the θz -plane from the point Q and $P(t)$ is given by Eq. (12). We note that the spatial variation of the pressure in Eq. (16) is the same as that obtained by Hassan and Batra [16] by fitting a polynomial function using the least square method through the experimental data given by Turkmen and Mecitolu [17] for a 22 cm x 22 cm specimen subjected to an air blast load. Similarly for the implosive loading, the pressure profile given by Eq. (16) is applied on the outer surface of the cylinder with the load pointing radially inwards while keeping the inner surface traction free. Equation (16) suggests that the pressure is maximum at point Q where $c = 0$. Figure 3(a),(b) depicts a schematic of the problem analyzed and the spatial distribution of the pressure over either the inner or the outer surface of the cylinder at time $t = 60 \mu\text{s}$. We use a uniform mesh with 432 8-node 2-D quadrilateral elements (16,128 DoF) and the time step size, $\Delta t = 0.01 \mu\text{s} \ll \Delta t_{\text{crit}} = 0.39 \mu\text{s}$ to obtain the transient solution.

Figure 3: (a) A schematic description of the problem analyzed and (b) spatial variation of the pressure

We have displayed in Fig. 4(a) time histories of the deflection, u , at two diametrically opposite points $L(0, 0.5b, 0.5a)$ and $L'(0, b, 0.5a)$ located on the mid-surface of the core. In Figs. 4(b) and 4(c), respectively, we have plotted the axial stress, σ_{zz} , and the hoop stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, at intersections of the mid-plane of each layer and the transverse normal passing through Q . We note that point L lies on the transverse normal passing through Q at which the pressure is maximum. The insets (a.1) and (a.2) in Fig. 4(a) represent the deformed shape of a cross-section at $z = 0.5a$ of the cylinder at $t = 60 \mu s$ for the explosive and the implosive loads, respectively. It is observed that after the first peak the amplitude of the radial displacement, u , at L decreases and that at L' increases with the passage of time due to the energy transfer in the cylinder since the energy does not dissipate in the absence of any damping. The axial stress and the hoop stress induced in the core are negligible as compared to that induced in the face sheets. Furthermore, the results reveal that the maximum deflection and the maximum axial stress in the cylinder for the implosive and the explosive loads are about equal in magnitude and opposite in sign; however the two maximum hoop stresses are not equal in magnitude. Thus the curvature of the cylinder affects the hoop stress at a point but not the axial stress and the radial displacement.

(a)

Figure 4: Time histories of (a) displacement, u , at $L(0, 0.5b, 0.5a)$ and $L'(0, b, 0.5a)$ on the mid-surface of the core, (b) axial stress, σ_{zz} , and (c) hoop stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, at L in the sandwich cylinder subjected to explosive and implosive loads given by Eq. (16). The insets (a.1) and (a.2) in (a) are the deformed shapes (magnified by a factor of 100) of a cross-section at $z = 0.5a$ of the cylinder subjected to the explosive and the implosive loads, respectively, at $t = 60 \mu s$ in which angles plotted on the circumferential coordinate axis are in degree and values on the radial coordinate axis are in mm.

In Fig. 5(a) we have exhibited the strain energy of deformation and the kinetic energy of the cylinder subjected to the implosive load, and illustrated that their sum, i.e., the total energy equals the work done by the external force (with 1.3% average difference between them). In Fig. 5(b) we have evinced components of the strain energy of deformation of the face sheets and the core which includes strain energies due to bending, transverse shear and transverse normal deformations. We note that the strain energy of bending deformations is the sum of strain energies due to in-plane axial and the shear stresses. It is found that bending deformations are dominant in the face sheets and transverse shear and transverse normal deformations are dominant in the core.

Figure 5: For the sandwich cylinder subjected to the implosive load (a) the strain energy of deformation, the kinetic energy, the total energy, and the work done by the external force and (b) components of the strain energy of deformation of the face sheets and the core

9 CONCLUSIONS

A third order shear and normal deformable shell theory (TSNDT) has been used for analyzing transient infinitesimal deformations of sandwich cylinders with the finite element method (FEM). It is established that the TSNDT accurately predicts the deformations of a cylinder without employing a

shear correction factor and using considerably fewer degrees of freedom than that required for analyzing the same problem using the 3-D linear elasticity theory and the FEM. It is found that when a sandwich cylinder is subjected to either an implosive or an explosive load, the face sheets and the core are mainly deformed in the bending and the transverse shear deformation modes, respectively. The curvature of the cylinder is found to have no significant effect on the deflection and the axial stress while it affects the hoop stress at a point in the cylinder.

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